

Conference Abstract

Evaluation of environmental research infrastructures services to address impacts on forest health and biodiversity

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Abstract

The potential of environmental research infrastructures (RIs) to fully implement the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles remains underutilised in addressing diverse challenges on global forest health and biodiversity. This study aims to characterise environmental RIs and their data services in tackling the effects of extreme climatic conditions on global forests. It examines the primary drivers of forest challenges across tropical, temperate, and boreal forest types, identifies the critical data required to understand these challenges, and explores the role and potential of environmental RIs in providing such data. A systematic literature search and review spanning 2013–2023 was conducted using sources such as Google, Google Scholar, and Scopus to identify documented key drivers of forest impacts, along with the relevant data types and sources utilised in the selected articles. The result has been organised in these four categories of drivers: **biophysical**, **biological**, **human-induced**, and **socioeconomic**. Furthermore, the numerous forest impacts identified are grouped into ecological, physiological, socioeconomic, and climate-related impacts. Different data types were considered in this study, ranging from carbon flux data to other various forms of experimental and field observation data. Data sources ranged from local and national forest inventories to specialized monitoring networks and research infrastructures. Four terrestrial biosphere

RIs—**ICOS**, **AnaEE**, **LifeWatch**, and **eLTER**—were assessed through their websites, annual reports, and impact assessments to evaluate their data services and potential contributions to climate change on global forests. The analysis explored the frequency and significance of integrating cross-RI multidisciplinary services. The study ultimately highlights existing gaps in RI data availability, accessibility, integration, and interoperability to address interconnected and overlapping global forest challenges.

Keywords

Research infrastructures, services, forest health, biodiversity, data types, data sources, FAIR, drivers, impacts, global challenges

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.